

Quality Asset Ability of Rhizobium Spciese from Organic Base Bio Fertilizer Production Using Multiple Organic waste as Carrier Base Inreadeness for Commercialization

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Abstract

Microorganisms work incognito to maintain the ecological balance by active participation in carbon, nitrogen, sulphur and phosphorous cycles in nature. Soil samples were collected from 12 sites, four from each of the study areas viz; NARICT farm land, Yankusa Land fill, and Sakadadi agricultural farm land . The total chromium content was analyzed using atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS). Physiochemical analysis of the contaminated and control land fill were also determined. The parameters determined were colour, odour, pH, temperature, Nitrogen, % potassium and % phosphorus etc. All parameters were found to be higher than the WHO limit except % Nitrogen, % Potassium and % Phosphorus that falls beyond. Further investigations were carried out to checkmate the proximate analysis of some nutritional values of Chemical fertilizer A and B as control while C for biofertilizer (treated) Most of the results computed shows there were significantly higher values in both macronutrient and micronutrient in Biofertilizer(C) production than those of the Chemical fertilizer (A and B). In view of the current investigation, bacteria isolates like those of (Rhizobium sp) namely; Rhizobium Japonicum, Rhizobium lupine etc were isolated as nitrogen fixing bacteria from root nodules of soya bean. Thus identification, and characterization rhyzobial sp for the production of biofertilizer In selective modified (MYEMA) through which propagation of bacteria mass cells were accentuated insitu. To this effect, the propagated mass cells of the bacteria were therefore meticulously and circumspectively mixed with multiple carrier base materials; for further utilization in the soils to increase its nutrient quality naturally after combining it with the soil. For nitrogen is one of the important component which acts as a building blocks of most biomolecules, but this inert nitrogen cannot be utilized by plants so the Rhizobium bacteria helps to fix the atmospheric nitrogen to ammonia which can be utilized by plants. In view of this study the production of biofertilizer from nitrogen fixing bacterial strains as well as utilizing them in the organic farming.

Key word: Rhozobium, Biofertilzer production, Multiple carrier organic base waste, Macro element/ microelement

INTRODUCTION

Nitrogen the essential component which serves as the building blocks of proteins and nucleic acids is abundant in the earth's atmosphere but it cannot be utilized by plants because of the inert nature of the nature due to the presence of triple bonds between the nitrogen atoms. So for the nitrogen to be used by plants it must be fixed or converted to the form of ammonium or nitrite ions. There are certain microorganisms which are capable of converting the atmospheric nitrogen into ammonia or nitrite ions by a process known as nitrogen fixation. These nitrogen fixation can be done by certain soil microbes both symbiotically and as well as non-symbiotically. So among the symbiotic nitrogen fixing bacteria *Rhizobium* has been found to be having a greatest activity in fixing these atmospheric nitrogen for plants and also increasing the soil fertility. In this way the *Rhizobium* bacterial strains can be utilized for production of bio-fertilizers. Bio-fertilizers are actually the natural mini-fertilizers which are responsible for providing safer plant nutrition and increasing the soil fertility through natural processes. These microorganisms actually can colonize the roots of different plants and the *rhizobium* can form root nodules in leguminous plants (Zahul islam, 2013). These *Rhizobial* inoculants after forming the root nodules fixes the atmospheric nitrogen to ammonia which can be utilized by plants.

Bio-fertilizers are the preparations of living cells of different strains of microorganisms that helps in enhancing the nutrient quality of soil by their interaction with the rhizosphere roots of plants when they are applied both on top soil and seed treatment. (Isolation of *azotobacter* and cost effective production of biofertilizer by Gomare et al., 2013). *Rhizobia* bacteria that fix N₂ (diazotroph) after becoming established inside root nodules of legumes (Fabaceae). The different genera of *rhizobia*, all of them belong to the *Rhizobial*, a probably monophyletic group of proteobacteria and they are soil bacteria characterized by their unique ability to infect root hairs of legumes and induce effective N₂-fixing nodules to form on the roots. They are rod shaped living plants which exist only in the vegetative stage. Unlike many other soil microorganisms, *rhizobia* produce no spores and they are aerobic and motile. (Matiru and Dakora, 2004). The *Rhizobial* inoculants colonize the roots of specific legumes to form tumor like growths called root nodules, which acts as factories of ammonia production. *Rhizobium* has ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen in symbiotic association with legumes and certain nonlegumes like *Parasponia*. Artificial seed inoculation is often needed to restore the population of effective strains of the *Rhizobium* near the rhizosphere to

hasten N-fixation. Each legume requires a specific species of *Rhizobium* to form effective nodules (Mishra et al., 2012)

In this research paper the main focus is in the isolation of Bacteria (*Rhizobium*) from soya bean root nodule of leguminous plants and it was further characterization followed by the identification through different biochemical tests for the identification, it's pure culture growth in selective and optimized media and then the mass production of the bacterial strain to be utilized as a bio-fertilizer

LITERATURE REVIEW

WHAT IS THE BIOFERTILIZER?

The term bio-fertilizer or called 'microbial inoculants' can be generally defined as natural fertilizer produce from either microbial inoculants of bacteria or algae or fungi separately or in combination which help biological fixation for the of plant growth

- a. Fixing nutrient availability in soil
 - b. Improves soil fertility
 - c. Readily converts complex organic compounds into simple soluble forms
- Accelerates mineral uptake by plants
- d. Increases crop yield
They help in building up soil micro-flora and there by soil health
 - e. Use of bio fertilizer is recommended for improving the soil fertility in organic farming
 - f. Stimulates plant growth
 - g. Provide resistance against drought and soil-borne diseases
 - h. Cost-effective .

a preparation containing live or latent cells of efficient strains of nitrogen fixing, phosphate solubilizing or cellulolytic microorganisms used for application of seed, soil or composting areas with the objective of increasing the numbers of such microorganisms and accelerate certain microbial process to augment the extent of the availability of nutrients in a form which can assimilated by plant (NIIR Board, 2004). In large sense, the term may be used to include all organic resources (manure) for plant growth which are rendered in an available form for plant absorption through microorganisms or plant associations or interactions (NIIR Board, 2004). The knowledge of applied microbial inoculums is long history which passes from generation to generation of

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farmers. It started with culture of small scale compost production that has evidently proved the ability of bio-fertilizer. This is recognize when the cultures accelerate the decomposition of organics residues and agricultural by-products through various processes and gives healthy harvest of crops (Abdul Halim, 2009). In Malaysia, industrial scale microbial inoculants are started in the late 1940's and peaking up in 1970's taking guide by *Brady rhizobium* inoculation on legumes. Government research institute, the Malaysian Rubber Board (MRB) had been conducting research on *Rhizobium* inoculums for leguminous cover crops in the inter rows of young rubber trees in the large plantations. Besides, University Putra Malaysia (UPM) also has conducted many researches since 1980's on *Mycorrhiza* and initiated the research to

BIOFERTILIZERS TYPES

a. *Rhizobium*: *Rhizobium* is a nitrogen fixing bacteria that colonizes the root nodules of legumous plants and is an effective bio-fertilizers (Sexena and tilak,1999). They are referred as cross inoculation group for being specific to form root nodules in legumous plants and has seven genera (Bookerd and singleton2002). For all legumous plants it is applied as seed inoculant (Tilak et al., 1992).

b. *Azotobacter*: Another nitrogen fixing bacteria inoculant that produces ample slime which aids in soil accretion e.g. *A. chroococcum* (Pandey and Kumar, 1987).

c. *Azospirillum*: Nitrogen fixing bacteria that colonizes the non-leguminous graminaceous plants rhizosphere and intercellular spaces of root cortex e.g. *Azospirillum lipoferum*, *A. brasilense*, *A. amazonense* (Balasubramanian and Kumar 1987). Besides these have the ability to reduce nitrate, denitrify etc (Kumar and Balasubramania, 1989). *Azospirillum* is inoculated through seed, seedling root dip and soil application methods.

d. *Cyanobacteria*: Free-living /symbiotic cyanobacteria is used as a bio-fertilizers for rice (Kaushi, 2014).

e. *Azolla*: *Azolla* is a free-floating water fern that fixes atmospheric nitrogen in association with Cyanobacteria : It is used as a bio-fertilizer for wetland rice (Kannaiyan, 1981).

f. Phosphate solubilizing microorganism: Microorganisms such as *Pseudomonas striata*., *Bacillus polymyxa*, *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus* etc secretes organic acids that causes dissolution of bound phosphates in soil (Khan et al ., 2007).

g. *Arbuscular Mycorrhiza*: Intracellular obligate fungal endosymbionts that possess vesicles for storage of nutrients and arbuscles for directing phosphorus, zinc and sulphur into the root system (Moses, 1973).

h. Silicate solubilizing bacteria: Some microbes are capable of dissolution silicates by secretion of organic acids like citric, oxalic acid etc (Ahmad et al., 2016). e.g. *Bacillus sp* (Zaidi et al., 2009).

i. Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria: Such inoculants are either bioprotectants (suppresses plant disease), biofertilizers (improves nutrient acquisition) or biostimulants (phytohormone production) . e.g *Pseudomonas* and *Bacillus* species (Ahemad, 2014).

BIO-FERTILIZER MAKING

The factors needed to be considered when making biofertilizers include the following: microbe's growth profile, types and optimum conditions of organism and formulation of inoculum. The formulation of inocula, method of application and storage of the products are all critical to the success of the biological product. In general, 6 steps are involved in making of bio-fertilizer. These steps are: choosing of active microorganisms, isolation and selection of target microbes, selection of method of propagation and carrier material, and phenotype testing, and large scale tests (Khosro and Yousef, 2012). First of all, decision must be made on the active microorganisms to be used. For example, it must be decided whether to use organic acid bacteria or nitrogen fixer or a combination of some organisms, after which target microbes are isolated. Usually, organisms are isolated from plant roots by luring it using a decoy such as placing cool rice underground beneath bamboo plants (Khosro and Yousef, 2012). Next, the isolated organism will be grown on Petri dishes before it is mass produces on flask. It is also important to choose the right carrier material. If the desire is to produce bio-fertilizer in powder form, then apioca flour or peat are the right carrier materials to use. Selection of propagation method is mainly to find out the optimum growth condition of organism. This can be achieved by determining growth profile under different parameter and conditions after which the phenotype is tested and selection is made. Lastly, the bio-fertilizer is tested on large scale at different environment to analyze its effectiveness and limitations (Khosro and Yousef, 2012).

CARRIER MATERIALS USED IN MAKING BIO-FERTILIZER

Bio-fertilizers are usually amended with carrier materials to increase bio-fertilizers effectiveness. It also increases water ration capacity (Ritika et al., 2014). According to

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(Somasegaran and Springer, 1994), stated that a good carrier material must have the following characteristics:

- it must be cheap and readily available in adequate amounts,
 - it must be easy to sterilize by autoclaving or gamma irradiation, it must be easy to process and must be free of lump-forming materials,
 - it must be non-toxic to both the microorganisms and the plants, to which it is applied,
 - it must have a good moisture absorption capacity,
 - it must have good water retention capacity of more than 50%,
 - it must have good adhesion to seeds, it must have good pH buffering capacity
 - it must have high organic matter content.
- Khosro and Yousef, (2012) stated that the incorporation of microorganisms into carrier materials enables easy handling, long term storage, and effectiveness of the bio-fertilizer.

They also stated that sterilization of carrier materials is essential to keep high numbers of inoculants on it during long storage period. Examples of carrier material include saw dust, talcum dust, manure, earthworm cast. Gamma-irradiation is the most suitable way of carrier sterilization, because the sterilization process makes no change in the physical and chemical properties of the material. Another method of carrier sterilization is autoclaving.

However, autoclaving may change the properties of some carrier materials resulting in the production of toxic substances that can kill some bacterial species (Hari and Perumal, 2010).

MOST IMPORTANT MICROORGANISMS USED IN BIOFERTILIZER

Organisms that are commonly used as bio-fertilizers component are nitrogen fixers (N-fixer), potassium solubilizer (K-solubilizer) and phosphorus solubilizer (P- solubilizer), or with the combination of molds or fungi. Most of the bacteria included in bio-fertilizer have close relationship with plant roots. *Rhizobium* has symbiotic interaction with legume roots, and Rhizobacteria inhabit on root surface or in rhizosphere soil. The phospho-microorganism mainly bacteria and fungi make insoluble phosphorus available to the plants (Gupta, 2004). Several soil bacteria and a few species of fungi possess the ability to bring insoluble phosphate in soil into soluble forms by secreting organic acids (Gupta, 2004). These acids lower the soil pH and bring about the dissolution of bound forms of phosphate. While *Rhizobium*, Blue Green Algae (BGA) and *Azolla* are crop specific, bio-inoculants like *Azotobacter*,

Azospirillum, Phosphorus Solubilizing Bacteria (PSB), Vesicular Arbuscular Mycorrhiza (VAM) could be regarded as broad spectrum biofertilizers (Gupta, 2004). VAM is fungi that are found associated with majority of agriculture crops and enhanced accumulation of plant nutrients (Gupta, 2004). It has also been suggested that VAM stimulate plant growth by physiological effects or by reducing the severity of diseases caused by the soil pathogens (Gupta, 2004). Examples of free living nitrogen fixing bacteria are obligate anaerobes (*Clostridium pasteurianum*), obligate aerobes (*Azotobacter*), facultative anaerobes, photosynthetic bacteria (*Rhodobacter*), cyanobacteria and some methanogens. The example of K solubilizer is *Bacillus mucilaginosus* while for P-solubilizer are *Bacillus megaterium*, *Bacillus circulans*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Pseudomonas straita*.

USES OF BIOFERTILIZERS

There are different methods of applying bio-fertilizers

- Coating on seed
- In soil at root system of plant
- Mixing with soil
- By dissolving into water

Used 50 ml water with 1% sucrose, boil for 10 min then add 1% gum Arabic allow to cool to form slurry which called as sticker solution. In sticker solution add 20 gm of bio-fertilizer mix it properly. Seeds were added to the slurry to form uniform coat of the culture around the seed without damaging seed coat. The inoculated seeds were kept on gunny bags away from sunlight for drying under shade and sown immediately (Malusa et al., 2012)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.2. Sample Collection:

Soil Samples

The soil samples were collected from Basawa farm land (A₁) NARICT farm Land (A₂) Sakadadi Farm land (A₃). Four samples were randomly collected from each site making a total of 12 samples. After the removal of surface litter, 20 gram of sample was collected from each of twelve sites at a depth between 10-15 cm using soils Augar into a clean polythene bag. All the samples were properly labeled (S₁-S₁₂) and transported to National Research Institute for Chemical Technology (NARICT), Basawa, Zaria at for analysis. Phase II Collection and extraction of root nodules from soya bean plants The experimental material for the present study was collected from NARICT Farm land Basawa Zaria. Plants Possessing healthy nodules with pink color were selected and transported to the lab

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NARICT. Root nodules of Soya Bean were used as study material for Isolation and further morphological and physiological characterization of rhizobium Strain. The roots were first washed thoroughly with sterile distilled water and nodules were Surface sterilized by washing with 95% ethanol for 10 seconds and again washed in Sterile distilled water for about 5 times. As seen in (plate 1 and 2)

Plate 1

Plate 2

Roots were mashed with pestle mortar to obtained Nodules and milky white substances of bacteroids by dipping in phosphate buffer Solution. (Collee and Miles, 1989).

CHOCOLATE BLOOD PASTE PREPARATION

Sterile Blood sample was specifically processed for sole source nitrogen which is best known as biocatalyst for microbial growth during urease base organic bio-fertilizer production. The sterile raw blood was conveyed right from the slaughter house to NARICT laboratory which is scientifically processed by boiling half way to form a semi digested protein. There upon the solution was filtered to obtain blood extract. An appreciable amount of salt was added to produce peptone extract; the solid blood residue was finally cut into choppy small substances using Knife and was finally blended using blender to obtain blood paste for nitrogen source in readiness for Rhizobium base organisms growth as picture in plate 3 and 4

Plate 3

Plate 4

2.4. ISOLATION OF NITROGEN FIXING BACTERIA (RHIZOBIUM) FROM CRUSH PROCESS ED ROOT NODULE SOYA BEAN USING MODIFIY YEMA MEDIUM(MYEMA)

Preparation of MYEMA medium, constituents of which are as follows:

The process crushed root nodule samples were suspended in water by vigorous vortexing and serial dilutions were made up to 10⁻⁶ in sterile distilled water. 100µl of appropriate dilution were added to petri plate on MYEM Agar plate containing the following

Chocolate Blood paste/ Blood extract	1000mi
NaCl	0.1g
K ₂ HPO ₄	0.5g
K ₂ SO ₄ .7H ₂ O/MgSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	1.0g
CaCl ₂	0.1g
Yellow puple (<i>Pakia biglobosa</i>) Dorowa	80g
Molasses	80g
Distilled water	1000ml
Agar	20g
pH	6.8-7

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and distilled water 1000 ml) with the right calibration of pH (6.8-7) and incubated for 24 hrs at 32°C. Bacterial culture was repeated for three times by single colony streaking on YEMA medium . The cultures were subsequently sub-cultured and used regularly. Agar slants were prepared and preserved at 70C for further experiments.

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION:

The colony characteristics (i.e. shape, size, color, elevation, margin of the bacterial colony and their growth rate) were determined by observing the colonies on MYEMA plates of the overnight grown microorganisms at 32°C. Microscopic observation of the Isolates was done using Gram staining technique. (Pervin et al., 2017)

BIOCHEMICAL TEST FOR RHIZOBIUM STRAINS :

Identification and biochemical characterization of bacterial strains Isolated colonies were characterized by different biochemical methods; methyl red test, VP test, Catalase test (cover slip method), starch hydrolysis test, citrate utilization test, and indole test. Catalase activity test, the presence of the enzyme catalase in the rhizobial isolates was examined by suspending one loopful of organism in a drop of 3% Hydrogen peroxide on a glass slide. This test was performed as per standard procedure (Deora and Singal 2010). Production of bubbles indicates a positive result for catalase test. Citrate utilization test, citrate utilization by the isolates was observed by the growth on slants of Simmon's Citrate Agar. A distinct change in color from green to blue refers to as a positive result for citrate utilization test.

IDENTIFICATION OF RHIZOBIUM STRAINS

The bacteria that were identified for Rhizobial organic Base bio-fertilizer are as follows: *Rhizobium Japonicum* , , *Rhizobium lupine Rhizobium meliloti* , *Rhizobium trifoli*, *Rhizobium phaseo*

2.7. Cultural and Metabolic Characterization:

Growth on 2% NaCl: To the basal medium of YEMA, 2% NaCl was added to check the growth of isolates. As 2% NaCl is inhibitory for some rhizobial isolates it may can serve as tools for identification of isolates.

Congo red test: The purity of the rhizobial isolates was detected by adding Congo red in YEMA media. Most rhizobia absorb the dye only weakly whereas contaminants including Agrobacteria, will absorb strongly. Bromothymol blue media: Yeast Mannitol

Agar (YMA) media incorporated with bromothymol blue was used to distinguish fast (acid producing) growing strains from slow (nonacid producing or alkali producing) growing rhizobia (Maatallah et al., 2002). In this medium, the fast growers require 48 hours to produce an acidic reaction by turning the color of the media yellow from green, whereas the slow growers take > 96 hours to produce alkaline endpoints with or without changing the color of the media from green to blue.

EXTRACTION OF ENZYME FROM RHIZOBIUM STRAIN

High speed refrigerated centrifuge was improvised and two days culture bacterial culture was poured into centrifuge tubes which was then allowed to spin for 20 minutes at 5000rpm after which the supernatant was decanted to obtain crude enzymes as seen plate 5

Plate 5

MULTIPLES CARRIER BASE MATERIAL USE FOR RHIZOBIUM PREPARATION BIOFERTILIZER STRAINS

1000ml of semi-digested blood extract/ an appreciable amount of NaCl was poured into 1000ml beaker, in a short while the solution was later turn into 6000ml pot. 2000ml of blood paste was meticulously introduced into the net resultant solution in the pot and 1000ml of distilled water which was then allowed to boil for 30 -40 minutes. After the solution was boiled for required desire then semi liquid 250g of Dorowa in addition to 250g of sugar cane molasses plus 250g of soya bean meal were dissolved in 3000ml bowl containing 1000ml of water to form a paste. The paste solution was later poured into the same pot for further boiling to obtain desire requirement. The semi liquid boiling solution was further added concomitantly with 250g of Dorowa, 250g of sugarcane molasses, 250g of soya bean meal respectively into the same boiling pot for a while until a semi solid paste was obtained once again. By and large 500g of rice husk bran, 500 dry blood powder meal ,

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sawdust respectively were concomitantly added to the semi-solid paste and there upon allowed to maintain its solidity before pour spray on a sterile tray. The semi-solid Rhizobium organic fertilizer was then sundry or oven dried at 37- 40°C (semi fermented Rhizobium organic fertilizer) alongside with the bacteria until its dried up to form a compost cake as seen in plate 6.

Plate 6

TEMPERATURE TOLERANCE

Temperature Tolerance was investigated by assaying the growth of bacterial cultures in YEMA medium at different temperature viz. 24° C, - 27-28° C, 35° C - 45° C.

ORGANIC BASE BIOFERTILIZER ARE DISPLAYED IN READINESS FOR PACKAGING, STORAGE AND FOR COMMERCIALIZATION

The polythene packets containing Rhizobium bacterial bio-fertilizers mixed with carrier materials were stored in cool place away from direct sunlight. The bio-fertilizer packets were then taken to the hilly regions for applications in different fields (Plate 7 .)

Plate 7

DETERMINATION OF THE PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF RHIZOBIUM BASE ORGANIC BIOFERTILIZER

pH:

Ten grams of the samples was taken and added to twenty five ml of distilled water. The mixture was shaken intermittently for 30 minutes. The pH was then determined by using the pH meter in standard bulb solution (Nag, 2007).

TEMPERATURE:

Ten grams of the sample was taken and added to 25ml of distilled water and the mixture was shaken thoroughly for 20 minutes. The temperature was determined using the thermometer in solution (Aneja, 2007)

ORGANIC CARBON

The method used was by (Fawole, and Oso, 2004). Two and half gram of dried, sample was taken into a pre-weight crucible and ignited over a Bunsen burner to a bright red heat, stirred occasionally with a wire loop. The sample was heated for 15 minutes. There upon it was then allowed to cool in a desiccators and the weight of buffing dust was taken. The organic carbon content was calculated as followed.

$$\frac{\text{Percentage organic matter}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100 = \frac{\text{loss in weight}}{\text{organic matter}} = 1.72$$

DETERMINATION OF ASH CONTENT

A porcelain crucible was dried in an oven at 100°C for 10 minutes, cooled in a desiccator and weighed (W_1). Two grams of the sample (buffing dust) was placed into the weighed porcelain crucible and re-weighed (W_2). It was then transferred into a furnace, which was set at 550°C. The sample was then left in the furnace for 6 hours to ensure proper aching. The crucible containing the ash was then removed cooled in the desiccators and weighted (W_3). The percentage ash content was calculated as:

$$\% \text{ Ash content} = \frac{W_3 - W_1}{W_2 - W_1} \times 100$$

Where,
 W_3 = weight of crucible and the content after cooling in the dessicator
 W_2 = weight of content and crucible before heating
 W_1 = weight of the crucible (AOAC, 1984)

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DETERMINATION OF CRUDE FIBER

Two grams of the finely sample was weighed out into a round bottom flask and mixed with 100 ml of 0.25M H₂SO₄. The solution was thoroughly mixed and boiled under reflux for 30 minutes. The hot solution was quickly filtered under suction. The insoluble matter was washed severally with hot water until it was acid free. This was later transferred into a flask and 100 ml of hot 0.31 M Na OH solution was added and the mixture boiled again under reflux for 30 minutes and then quickly filtered under suction. The soluble residue was washed with boiling water until it was base free and later dried to a constant weight in the oven at 100°C and finally cooled in a dessicator and weighed (C₁)

The weighed sample (C₂) was then incinerated in a Gallekamp (80) muffle furnace at 550°C

$$\% \text{ crude fibre} = \frac{C_1 - C_2}{\text{Wt of sample}} \times 100 \quad (\text{AOAC, 1984})$$

ORGANIC MATTER:

Two and a half grams of dried, sample was taken into a pre-weighed crucible and ignited over a Bunsen burner to a bright red heat, stirring occasionally with a wire loop. The sample was heated for 15 minutes. Then it was allowed to cool in a desiccator and the weight of the soil was taken. The organic carbon content was calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ Organic matter} = \frac{\text{loss in weight}}{\text{Weight of Sample}} \times 100$$

Fawole and Oso, (2004).

DETERMINATION OF TOTAL CARBOHYDRATE CONTENT

The total carbohydrate content of the sample was obtained as described by Moronkola *et al.*, (2011), where the results from fat, protein, moisture and ash content analyses were sum-up and the carbohydrate content was calculated as follows: 100 - (% moisture + % protein + % fat + % ash)

TOTAL NITROGEN: (N)

One and a half gram of crushed dried samples was pour into 300ml Kjeldahl flask along with 25ml of concentration. H₂SO₄ and 3g mixed catalyst. The sample was digested using Kjeldahl digestion apparatus until a clear green or whitish color was obtained. The digested solution was then diluted to 100ml with distilled water. Distillation was done adding 20ml of diluted digest into

500ml Kjeldahl flask containing anti - bumping chips and 40ml of 40% NaOH was slowly added by the side of the flask. A conical flask (250ml) containing a mixture of 50ml 2% boric acid and 4 drops of mixed indicator (Cresol/bromothymol) was used to trap the liberated ammonia. The distillate was then titrated with 0.1M HCL. The total nitrogen content was then calculated using

$$\%N_2 = \frac{14 \times M \times V + x \times V}{\text{weight of sample (mg)} \times V_S} \times 100$$

Where M = Actual molarity of acid

V = Titre volume of HCL used

V+ = Aliquot volume distilled

(Onyeika and Osieji 2003).

PHOSPHORUS:(P)

Fifty grams of the dried crushed Rhizobium organic base Biofertilizer was suspended and filtered through a nylon cloth into a glass beaker. Twenty five ml of the filtrate was heated for 25 minutes with HNO₃/HCL in a ratio of 3:1 (digestion). The mixture was dilute was diluted to the 100ml mark with distilled water. Fifteen ml of the diluted solution was then pipette into a cuvette and 1ml of the phosphate reagent was added to it and the reading taken using the phosphate meter (Nag, 2007).

POTASSIUM (K)

To determine the potassium content of the samples fifty grams of the dried Urease organic base Bio-fertilizer was suspended in 50ml of distilled water and filtered using nylon cloth. The filtrate (25 ml) was mixed with HNO₃/HClO₄ (ratio 2:1). The beaker containing the mixture was then placed on a hot plate and boiled until the solution became clear. This was then filtered using what man filter paper No.1 in a volumetric flask and the volume of the filtrate was made up to 100 ml by the addition of deionized water digested sample was stored in a sterile polyethylene bottle at room temperature for further analysis of the metal using atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

Calculation

$$\% \text{ Potassium} = 2 \times 0.005$$

Where R = Potassium Concentration (ppm) in the aliquot (Nag, 2007).

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MANGANESE DETERMINATION

Hundred ml of urease organic base bio-fertilizer sample was processed from hundred gram of the sample. After which 5ml special reagent was added. There upon it was concentrated up to 90ml through boiling. 1g of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ was added and was later boiled for 1 minute. After which the removal of the heated solution from the heat source was later allowed to stand for 1 minute. The solution was then diluted to 100ml with distilled water. Finally preparation of standard containing 100- 1500 μg manganese was treated using treated using various amounts of standard manganese solution in like manner.

Calculation

Manganese $\text{mg/l} = \mu\text{g}(\text{in } 100\text{ml final volume/ ml sample})$ (Nag 2007)

MAGNESIUM DETERMINATION

Fifty ml of Rhizobium organic base bio-fertilizer was processed from fifty 50 g of sample. Concomitantly, a few ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCl) was added to the solution. There with, 10ml of 10% solution of ammonium chloride was added to make alkaline with concentrated ammonium hydroxide and was gently boiled for a few minute. Constant stirring of the solution to warmness was made after which 10 ml of saturated solution of ammonium oxalate was added too. In the process of time the solution was allowed to stand for 30minutes. Filtration was followed using quantitative filter paper on a funnel. Soon after, a concentration of ammonium hydroxide to filtrate was made up to equality of one-ninth of its volume. Furthermore 10ml of 10% solution of diammonium hydrogen phosphate was added to the solution for at least 3hours and then finally filtered. Thereupon the folder paper was transferred a long side with magnesium precipitate in a weigh crucible. Soon after the precipitate was thoroughly dried in a hot air oven and therewith the crucible was ignited along side with magnesium precipitate for 3 minutes at 1000°C . Finally the crucible along with precipitate was maintained in a dessicator/ crucible until constant weight was duly obtained

Calculation

Magnesium $\text{mg/litre} = \text{mg Mg } 2 \text{ P}2\text{O}7 \times 218.4/\text{ml of sample.}$ (Nag 2007)

Total Chromium

Fifty gram of the dried crushed soil was suspended in 50ml distilled water in a beaker and was filtered through nylon cloth. Twenty five of the filtrate was collected in a 400ml beaker and 10ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 and 5ml of concentrated HNO_3 were added to the filtrate in ratio3/1. The beaker containing the mixture was then placed on a hot plate for boiling until the solution becomes clear and then the solution was transferred by filtration through what man Filter paper NO2 into a volumetric flask. The volume of the filtrate was made up to 50ml by adding deionised water. Digested sample were store in sterile polyethylene bottles at room temperature for further analysis of the metal using flame atomic absorption spectrometry (FAAS) Rani, 2003.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The present report gave a survey of Rhizobial genera occurring in the Rhhizospheric zone of soya bean plants. Particular attention was basically focused on to those strains that might positively affect the growth of the plants following the algorithm of inoculation into the Rhizoshere; base on morphological characters of Rhizobial genera isolated from the Rhizosheric area of soya bean root. The isolates were circular in shape with entire margin and milky cream to watery translucent appearance on modify processed meat extract and Molasses/ "Dorowa" (*Parkia biglobosa*) pulp powder agar medium as natural glucose. It was meticulously found that the strain grown showed the convex elevation on the newly improve YEMA medium. The colonies were 2.5mm translucent whitish and glittering in plate 8 and 9 poster.

Plate 8

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Plate 9

Roychowdhury *et al.*, (2015) showed the growth of Rhizobium bacterial on Congo red yeast extract mannitol agar medium. Rhizobial isolates were tentatively assigned to genera mesorhizobium on the basis of morphological characters. Similarly, (Rai *et al.*, 2013) and (Gauri *et al.*, 2012) also characterized meso-rhizobial isolates of the basis of their colony shape, color, and texture. Datta *et al.*, (2013) also found that Rhizobium were Gram negative, motile, rod shaped and were fast grower as they showed convex elevation in the newly improve meat extract natural glucose “Dorowa” agar medium. Table 1 represent the morphological and cultural characteristic of the strains indicating Rhizobium. Gram’s staining of the isolates was confirmed by microscopic observations and the Mesorhizobium sp was found to be gram negative. (Gauri *et al.*, (2012) also reported the microscopic examination of Rhizobium revealed the isolates to be gram negative. Roychowdhury *et al.*, (2015) observe his strains under the microscope by gram staining which showed white pinkish color and rod shape bacterial. Furthermore all the strains were also subjected to different biochemical test like those of Methyl red test, voges proskaur test, indole test, catalase test, urease test, citrate utilization test etc respectively. Thus some strains gave negative as well as positive results of the true nature of the said Rhizobial genera in their sequential order. The study was simultaneously and vividly checkmated to be in line with (Brown *et al.*, 1962).

Generally speaking the synergy symbiotic nitrogen fixation relationship between the root and the Rhizobium are so restricted by so many factors. In view of the current investigation in Table 2 regarding to pH and temperature in-situ, temperature and pH are the major physical parameter that determine the growth and activities of microorganisms in a given habitat. With respect to table 2 the control modified medium conditioned at 3.0, 4.0, 6.0, and 7.0 reveals that the

rhizobium sp thrived at pH 6 to 7. According to(Deora and Sinhel, 2010) have proposed that slight variation in the pH of the medium might have an enormous effect on the growth of Rhizobium Sp. Rhizobial isolates were observed to be more sensitive to low pH than their host and this affect the consortium establishment of the symbiosis, limiting the survival and persistence of the rhizobia (Zahran, 1999). On the other hand Temperature is also one of the major factors affecting Rhizobia growth, survival in the soil and the symbiotic process its self(Niste *et al.*, 2013). High soil temperature in the tropic have always been a major constrains of Rhizobial consortium for BNF in legumes crops. High temperature may affect symbiotic relationships, nitrogen content, formation of roots and binding of rhizobia to root hairs, nodule development and function and dry matter production (Boboye *et al.*, 2011). Low temperature affect nodulation as the process of nodule initiation is completely inhibited under low (Sadolosky, 2005). High temperature also alters the pattern of cell surfaces components (EPS and LPS) secreted by Rhizobia which in turn negatively affect the process of nodulation and N₂ fixation(Yadav *et al.*, 2010).

Bacteria have developed controlled system to differentiate and cope up with harmful metal ions at minimal concentration. Assessing the effect of metal salts on Rhizobial strains showed that all the strains were sensitive to Mercury Chloride(HgCl) Chromium Sulphate(CrSO₄) and Copper Sulphate (CuSO₄), while ZnSO₄ and CaSO₄ on Rhizobia growth show a bit of tolerance growth level of ZnSO₄ and CaSO₄ up to optimal concentration of 2% in table 3. The study reveals that most metals ion whenever they are opportune to enter bacterial cells they normally produced physiological and toxic effect to bacteria at minimal concentration, but a high concentration level the reverse is the case(deadly to microorganisms) (Datta *et al.*, 2015)

In trying to determine the physiochemical characteristics of the soil and the presence of chromium ions in environment due to their toxicity is of great concerned to public health and environment. The data showed the level at which the polluted landfill has been fully devastated due to the discharged of industrial chemical recipe. The unprecedented discharge of effluent containing chromium ions could be dully mitigated or resuscitated by the abating land through bioremediation process.

Discharge of tannery effluent containing chromium ion in to the environment can produce considerable

modification of their microbial populations, reducing their activity and number in their consortia in a given habitat. The present study, is mainly focused on soil samples collected from control landfill (Yankusa), contaminated land fill (Gasau) respectively and tannery effluent from different sources of industrial discharge in to the soil. The emissions of effluent containing toxic chemical recipe have drastically rendered the virgin soil unproductive and devastated to plants and animals (Zafar et al., 2007).

Soil is a potent system of terrestrial system, and direct discharge of industrial tannery effluent especially that without treatment may have profound influence on physiochemical and biological properties of soil fertility (Narasimba et al., 2011).

Analysis of the soil at the study site showed that the contaminated landfill soil differ from soil, from the control site as shown in table 4 : The color is usually the first parameter to be recognized in control and polluted landfill due to contaminated waste water that affect the integrity of the land mass. Such colors were observed to be brown and blue/black in their identity and were symbolized with label (S₁, S₂, S₃ and S₄), (S₅, S₆, S₇, and S₈) from control sample and contaminated site respectively (Dhungana and Yadav, 2009). WHO reported colorless, dirty dark green and green appearance for tannery effluents in like manner affect the color, appearance and permeability of the virgin soil when discharge. Obnoxious odor is also perceived and recognized within the affected area of effluent discharge compared with the reference soil sample as shown in table 4. The mean pH values of NARICT farm land was found to be weekly acidic in comparison with (6.87) Yankusa control site as shown in table 4 is not in compliance with the WHO standard. Jyoshana and Narasimba (2007) reports show that discharge of effluent from tannery increased the soil pH slightly in comparison with the control Yankusa landfill soil with pH 5.12 and pH 6.8 from NARICT farm land. Variation in pH values of effluent waste to soils can alter the rate of biological reaction and survival of various microorganisms. Since the control landfill does not contained chemicals recipe. The organisms absolutely and sincerely maintained their level of integrity in terms of improving the soil fertility for their survival as well as the life of plants and animals (Bannats et al., 2008). The varying pH could be attributed to the chemical discharge on landfill due to excessive use of NaOH, H₂O₂ and atomic stabilizer use during finishing processes in tanning and in conjunction with environmental stresses brought about by the contamination (Wood and Kellong, 2007). The soil samples collected from polluted sites

were mostly affected by waste water irrigation due to the presence of heavy metal which affects the pH and might likely reduced the population densities of micro flora within a given habitat.

The mean temperature values of NARICT farm land were (37°C) in comparison with the reference soil sample (37°C) Yankusa. The findings are in line with the study conducted by Nandakumar (2008). It appears the values falls within the permissible limit. It might be that at the time the sample were collected at winter season, the reference water sample falls within the ambient temperature and other below. High temperature could be as a result of addition of warm water while low temperature could be attributable for the season of samples collection (winter). Increase in temperature can cause change in the species in a given habitat. It could also reduce solubility of oxygen and amplified odour due to anaerobic and aerobic reaction respectively (Nandakumar, 2008).

The total chromium content of the contamination soil were also much higher than that of the control as observed in table 4. With varying values ranging between (1.28- 4.15mg/l) from NARICT farm land, (8.36 – 107.99mg/l) from Yankusa control land fill, (1.93- 4.8mg/l) Sakadadi farm land respectively. The study is in line with the result conducted priorily by (Ugoji and Aboaba, 2004). Total chromium implies (II), Chromium (III) chromate ion and chromium (VI) ion present in natural water or contaminated soil. Their presence in a given habitat depend on interaction with microbes that led to the significantly differed in biological, geo chemical and toxicological properties (Sule and Ingle, 1996). Cr(III) over a narrow concentration range is considered essential for mammals, maintenance of glucose essential for mammals, lipid and protein metabolism at minimal level, whereas Cr(VI) is reported to have a toxic effect in human (Cotton et al., 1999). In this current investigation, tannery effluent discharged directly on land fill are usually found to contain higher values of chromium in comparison with the two farm lands NARICT and Sakadadi. According to (Ugoji Aboaba 2004), chromium ion in polluted land had higher concentration 89.30% against the lower values of 0.255mg/l in the control land. However, a possible explanation for its high level is as a result of the used chromium salt during tanning. This could be disastrous to the concept of a clean environment. It might also enter the food chain through plants, animals as well as water source. Once it gets into food chains by, bioaccumulations, bio-magnification as well as recalcitrant to toxicity of the metal in various living

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system may take place. This result was in conformity with that of (Khan, 2006), in which they reported that bioaccumulation, and biomagnifications could possibly led to toxic level of these metals in organism, even if exposure level is very low. Hence this could also cause disruption in the ecological balance when in abundance. However, the said permissible limit for total chromium discharge in the stream or river for irrigation and domestic use should not exceed 0.05mg/l by (WHO, 1985). Further observations were made in such a way that it could be that the rural dwellers who lives within that particular vicinity are not guaranteed of safety. High concentrations of chromium in drinking water can cause skin ulcer, allergic reactions, carcinogenic and mutagenic effect to humans (Matin and Ginswold, 2009). Total nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium (NPK) in percentages were higher in all ramifications from contaminated land fill sites of Yankusa control than those of the both agricultural farm land of (NARICT) and (SAKADADI); except, Potassium content. The properties of contaminated soil samples were (0.460, 0.293) and 0.100%;(0.385,0.040) and 0.063%;(0.385,0.973 and 1.043%)respectively. However this could be possibly explain that surface run-offs from agriculturally fertilized and neighboring lands and the microbes in converting inorganic element to organic compound (Mineralization). This might have contributed significantly to the lesser amount of phosphate and nitrogen percentages present in Yankusa control land fill in comparison to both agricultural farm lands of NARICT and Sakadadi Zaria respectively. Could this be a plause? Except Potassium. On the hand of the essential elements one could have expected the sequence of assimilation to be in this order $N > P > K$ but instead $N < P < K$. This might be related to the possible use of high amount of fertilizers during such periods by neighboring farmers. In addition, surface runoffs could attributably added to the nutrients during rainfall. Thus most especially as reaches to the peak of rainy season period in the area under study. To this effect there seems to be low content of Phosphate than nitrates. This might also be related to the fact that some aquatic photosynthetic microorganisms utilized phosphate while oxygen-depleted photosporylative means of energy generated (Mittal et al., 2012). The order of this trench $N > P > K$, nitrate might seem to be less abundant than Phosphorus , for which reason it may therefore be that nitrate could be said to be a limiting nutrient in the productivity of Yankusa Land fill.

The results in table 4 showing the pH differences for chemical fertilizer A and B with mean average was

found to be 6.8 (week acid) while for the bio-fertilizer was 7.0(Neutral). Varying in pH values of the both the chemical fertilizers (A and B) as well as for bio-fertilizer(C) in the soil might altered the rate of biological reaction and the survival of various microorganisms at this particular range of pH 6.8 and 7.0. Thus the organisms might absolutely and sincerely maintained their level of integrity in terms of improving the soil fertility for their survival as well as the life of plants and animals(Bonnate et al., 2008). The varying in the pH of both chemical fertilizer(A and B) could also attributed to the chemical content . Moisture content for both Chemical fertilizer (A and B) deferred from one another was based on the formulation composition and ranged between 19.24% – 20.60% while the bio-fertilizer C was found to be 21.31%. Varying in the moisture content of each respected fertilizer could also be as a result of composting decrease due to incubation period because . Thus the inoculation of the biofertilizer with EM increased the temperature and decrease the moisture content bio-fertilizer and the reverse is more or less the same to chemical fertilizer. The same phenomenal has also been notified in open field composting (Mittal et al., 2012). There was also varying of ash content that was notice within the axes of chemical fertilizer which had fallen between the range of 1.5%- 2.24% as well as for the bio-fertilizer which was observed to be 4.21. This could be attributably due to the maturity of composting, the ash content significantly increase during preparation. Since the organic materials were decomposed to form the metabolic gases (Chang and Yang,2009). In the process of time there were gradual increase of crude fiber starting from both chemical fertilizer A and B at the ranged of 1.22% and the highest was observed from bio-fertilizer with 4.21%. the results of crude fiber were in agreement with the findings of (Bolaji et al., 2009) and Chery et al., 2014) respectively. On the contrary (singh and subudhi 1978) reported less values and it ranged between 9.1- 13.07%, while (Abiodun and Adepeju, 2011) was reported 12.7 % CF; this could also due to changes in the dry matter of both chemical fertilizer and Bio-fertilizer.

Nutrient present for both chemical fertilizer A and B as well as for Bio-fertilizer(C) present in this case study can be categorized in to Macro-element t(NPK) Ca mg etc and microelement and Manganese (Mn) , Boron (Bo), Sulphur(S), Cupper(Cu) etc respectively. The results indicated that the macro and Micro nutrient content in Control chemical fertilizer as well as for Bio-fertilizer (treated) shows that the bio-fertilizer(C) had the highest nutrient content, followed by the respective

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chemical fertilizer (A and B) in the chronological order. According to (Barak,1999) Nitrogen is a major requirement for high yield of cereal crops and Nitrogen fertilization are often essential on soil of low organic matter as could be visualized or observed in table 4. Crops response to Nitrogen fertilizer is influence by factors such as Nitrogen fertilizer management soil types , crop sequence and supply of residual and mineralized nitrogen(Mangel and Kirkby 1987). Nitrogen presence in plant leads to the stimulation of leaf growth and stem; it's also gave a green coloration of the leaves. Deficiencies; lack of nitrogen is often indicated by yellowish colour of the leave and short growth of the stalk. As seen plate 10 and 11

Potassium (K) Acts as a catalyst or activator of enzymes promotes overall growth, critical for stomata turgor deficiencies; Poor growth, leaf chlorosis/necrosis (death), slowed gas exchange (Mifilinge et al., 2014) Other micro element in table 5 like those of Boron(Bo), iron(Fe), Manganese (Mn) etc were significantly play a crucial role in plant, animal as well as microorganism growth in-situ. Iron (Fe) acts as a catalyst for enzymes involved in Chlorophyll production, protein synthesis, respiration and other reactions; deficiencies in Fe could cause interveinal chlorosis of young leaves. Manganase(Mn) is involved in enzyme activation during carbohydrate reduction, Chlorophyll and RNA/DNA synthesis; deficiencies could led to interveinal chlorosis of young leaves necrotic spots, leaf (Bakonyi et al., 2013).

Plate 10

Plate 11

(Mifilinge et al., 2014). Phosphorus is also one of the major element required for plant growth and higher yield this element is necessary for the nodulation by Rhizobium and even to nitrogen fixer. The phosphor-microorganism manly bacteria and fungi make available insoluble phosphorus to the plant. The root fungi association or mycorrhiza has high potential in accumulating phosphorus in the plant (Kumar et al ., 2010).

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Table1 : MORPHOLOGY AND BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF RHIZOBIAL STRAINS ISOLATES

Character	Rhizobium Japonicum	Rhizobium lupine	Rhizobium meliloti	Rhizobium trifoli	Rhizobium Phaseo
Umbonate colony	-	+	-	-	-
Trimethylamine odour	-	+	-	-	-
Rod	Rods	Rods	Rods	Rods	Rods
Pigment/production	White	White	White	White	White
Motility	+	+	+	-	-
Swarming	-	-	-	-	-
Sporeformation	-	-	-	-	-
Gram reaction	-	-	-	-	-
Aerobid facuta (A)	A/FA	A	F/A	F/A	F.A
Catalase activities	+	+	+	+	+
Oxidase activity	+	+	+	+	+
Gelatin liquid faction	+	+/-	+	+/-	+/-
Indole production	ND	+	+	+	+
Citrate utilization	-	-	-	-	-
Urease activities	ND	ND	+	+	+/-
H ₂ s. production	ND	ND	+	-	-
Methyl red	ND	ND	-	-	-
Vogesproskau	ND	ND	-	-	-
Lactose	+	-	-	+	+
Glucose	+	+/-	+	+	+/-

Key=characters for which different general score positive (+) negative (-) ND = Not done

TABLE2 : EFFECT OF PH AND TEMPERATURE ON TOLERANCE LEVEL OF RHIZOBIM STRAINS AT 0.1 % -1% ZNSO4/CASO4 CONCENTRATION IN MODIFIED RHIOBIUM GROWTH AGAR (MRA)

Isolates	Colony growth mm at 0.1% concentration (maximum)								
	pH					Temperature °C			
	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	7.0	24	27—32	35—45	
<i>Rhizobium Japonicum</i>	--	+	-	+	+++ -	--	++++	++	
<i>Rhizobium lupine</i>	--	+	--	+	++++	--	+++	++	
<i>Rhizobium meliloti</i>	--	+	+++	+	++++	--	+++	+	
<i>Rhizobium trifoli</i>	--	+	+	--	++++	--	+++	++	
<i>Rhizobium Phaseo</i>	-	-	-	-	++++	-	+++	+	
KEY	++++ Abundant growth		+++ Moderate growth		++ Scarce		+ Less		- None

TABLE 3. EFFECT OF METAL IONS ON GROWTH OF RHIZOBIA

Metal salt	Rhizobial strains	%growth concentration			
		0.0	0.1	1	2
Hgcl2	Rhizibial sp	+	-	-	-
CrSO4	“	+	-	-	-
ZnSO4	“	+	+	+	+
CaSO4	“	+	+	+	+
CuSO4	“	+	-	-	-

Table 4. PHYSICOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SOIL SAMPLES

PROPERTIES	NARICT FARM LAND				YANKUSA LANDFIL				SAKADADI FARM LAND			
	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	S ₁₀	S ₁₁	S ₁₂
Colour	Br	Br	Br	Br								
Odour	Nor	Nor	Nor	Nor	Foul	Foul	Foul	Foul	Nor	Nor	Nor	Nor
pH	7.0	6.8	6.9	6.8	5.6	5.3	5.7	3.9	7.0	6.7	6.9	6.8
Temperature	35 ⁰ c	37 ⁰ c	33 ⁰ c	33 ⁰ c	37 ⁰ c	36 ⁰ c	35 ⁰ c	40 ⁰ c	37 ⁰ c	34 ⁰ c	34 ⁰ c	34 ⁰ c
Cr(mgIL)	2.18	4.15	1.32	1.28	8.36	107.99	67.25	81.52	4.43	4.48	1.50	1.93
%N	0.14	0.09	0.19	0.19	3.20	0.23	1.03	0.37	0.33	0.33	0.37	0.14
%K	0.612	1.16	1.16	1.24	0.05	0.16	0.26	1.07	0.87	0.40	1.30	1.32
%P	0.025	0.057	0.013	0.012	0.156	0.201	0.233	0.013	0.011	0.047	0.077	0.023

KEY Br= Brown; Nor= Normal; Foul= fairly foul ; Site= S₁-S₁₂

Table 5 MACRO AND MICRO NUTRIENT AND OTHER CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF CHEMICAL(CONTROL) / BIOFERTILIZER A B C

Fer/Bio f Form	Percentage (%)											Concentration mg/l			
	pH %	Mois %	Ash %	Crude Fiber %	Carbon %	Carbo Hydrate %	N	P	K	mg	Ca	B	Fe	Mn	Mo
A	6.8	19.24	1.50	1.22	7.20	24.12	12.11	13.01	10.0	0.20	0.51	0.30	0.21	0.03	0.004
B	6.7	20.60	2.24	2.21	12.22	34.35	13.51	12.52	13.54	0.21	0.60	0.51	0.23	0.05	0.003
C	7.0	21.31	4.21	2.42	18.23	44.25	20.30	22.21	24.30	0.42	0.90	0.32	0.45	0.07	0.003

KEY A Chemical fertilizer; B =Chemical fertilizer; C= Biofertilizer

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CONCLUSION

Our dependence on chemical fertilizers and pesticides has encouraged the thriving of industries that are producing life-threatening chemicals which are not only hazardous for human consumption but can also disturb the ecological balance. As a matter of truth, attention is now shifting from consuming food grown with chemical fertilizers to food grown with organic fertilizers because of the harmful effects that these foods have in the body when consumed. Biofertilizers can help solve the problem of food need of the ever increasing global population. In this research other important parameter considered for physical and chemical characteristics profile of soil showed at start of experiment inadequate NPK for plantation and after the use of appropriate biofertilizer profile is potentially improved. In further study media optimization for growth of new improved inoculant may contain Rhizobia and PGP organisms for design of biofertilizer. The new technology when developed using the tool of molecular biotechnology can enhance the biological pathways of production of phytohormones if identified and transferred to the useful plant growth promoting rhizobacteria. This technology will help provide relief from environmental stresses. However, the ignorance regarding improved protocols of bio-fertilizers application to the field is one of the few limiting factors to bio-fertilizers usage.

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CONTROL LANDFILL (YANKUSA) plate 12

Plate 13

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